

Reframing Transition Pathways and Values Through System Innovation Across 9 European Regions.

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Abstract

This is an account of an ongoing participatory research involving 9 European regions at the forefront of climate change. Within the framework of ARSINOE, a Horizon 2020 project developing regional adaptation pathways and strategies across 15 countries, we implement the System Innovation Approach, a practice-based framework for innovation based on Living Labs where diverse pools of stakeholders self-assess the state of their system and co-design adaptation pathways. Living Labs are developed through a series of three workshops, each with a particular focus.

Preliminary results show that the specifics of each territory act as triggers of situated strategies and actions that respond to challenges in novel ways. Beyond local problem-solving, the process reveals that 1) reframing problems from a holistic perspective is essential to unveil major blockers and opportunities currently overshadowed by partial viewpoints; 2) community well-being and care are perceived by Living Lab participants as core drivers for collective action; 3) finding new ways to address long-term social trends and transforming existing legal and financial frameworks are crucial to leveraging positive transitions; 4) the main types of innovations required are socio-technical, rather than technological, in nature.

Key words

Resilience, innovation, climate change, participatory research.

Introduction to ARSINOE

ARSINOE – Climate-resilient Regions Through Systemic Solutions and Innovations – is a Horizon 2020 project that aims to build an ecosystem for innovative climate change adaptation across Europe. Coordinated by the University of Thessaly (Greece), it brings together 41 partners from 15 countries gathered in 9 case studies to co-design innovative pathways for resilience with local stakeholders through a participatory process.

Case studies are designed to address specific climate-related challenges, such as urban heatwaves, flooding, water management, heritage preservation, and biodiversity loss. The selected regions are the Athens metropolitan area (case study 1), Mediterranean ports (case study 2), the Main river region in Germany (case study 3), the transboundary Ohrid and Prespa lakes region (case study 4), the Canary Islands (case study 5), the transboundary Black Sea region (case study 6), Southern Denmark (case study 7), the Torbay & Devon County in the United Kingdom (case study 8) and the island of Sardinia (case study 9).

Figure 1. The nine ARSINOE Case Studies

System Innovation Approach and the Living Labs

Complexity results from the interconnectedness of interactions between different subsystems and their environment [1]. Because climate-related problems are open, complex, dynamic, and networked, they cannot be split up into smaller parts that could be dealt with more easily (as in conventional problem-solving), without risking severing key relations, that will need to be re-established later in the problem-solving process, “when they will present themselves as

flaws in the solution or, indeed, as fresh problems” [2:10]. Moreover, while problems are often framed from technical perspectives alone, yet excessive focus on technical aspects may prove harmful in the longer run: “When new technologies are used to eliminate well-understood system failures or to gain high precision performance, they often introduce new pathways to large scale, catastrophic failures. [...] these new, rare catastrophes have an even greater impact than those eliminated by the new technology” [2]. Therefore, even though our goal is to find solutions, it is questions, not answers, that we need to look for, because once problems are correctly framed, solutions immediately exist. All that is needed is to *dis-cover* them, as Bergson famously argued. Hence, the main innovation in our project lies not at the level of solutions, but at that of problem framing, which, in return, produces innovative outcomes at various levels.

Because human practitioners are the adaptable element in such systems [2], it is crucial that challenges are framed through a dynamic, multi-stakeholder perspective.

Within ARSINOE, we implement the System Innovation Approach (SIA), a methodological framework based on Living Labs, where a diverse pool of stakeholders self-assesses the state of their system, work together toward transformative visions, and co-design adaptation pathways for their region. SIA relies on systems thinking, design methods, and situated knowledge to address complex challenges, by examining the underlying structure of a system, seeing relationships, patterns, and cycles [3]. Local Living Labs produce visions of the future that describe the values, functions, order, and means shared among stakeholders, aligning interests and framing problems as the process unfolds. Then, trajectories to face climate challenges are co-created, enabling experts, decision-makers, and citizens to move beyond the current state and envision future scenarios that deviate from the expected course of actions through transformative actions at multiple levels.

Through SIA, we assess interconnectedness among system components (decisions, decision-makers, stakeholders, resources, organizational setups, emergent behaviors, and cultural identity), within a specific time frame. This broad view can help identify the structural causes of issues and know just where to work to address them.

ARSINOE’s Living Labs take the form of three workshops. Convened every 6 months, each one addresses a specific goal and produces a pre-defined set of outputs. The first workshop’s main goal is *mapping*. Participants draw a mental map of the system’s current state, including stakeholders, processes, issues, and challenges, and formulate a *problem statement*. This material serves as the basis for *envisioning*, –the second workshop’s main activity–, with the goal of producing a *future vision* for the region and defining a timeframe for transformation. Finally, during the *backcasting* exercise carried out in the third workshop, participants co-design *pathways for resilience, adaptation, and sustainability*, working backward from the

future vision produced in workshop 2.

So far, we have implemented the first two rounds of workshops across the nine case studies and are about to begin the third. Convening the first workshops was often challenging: sometimes, stakeholders envisioned Living Labs as ways to validate pre-existing strategies, policies, and plans; in other cases, research teams saw workshops more as spaces for data collection than as opportunities for problem refinement. An important shift in perspectives took place during the process, as participants began to take ownership and carry the workshop's concerns beyond their initial circle.

The following section provides an overview of the general trends observed during the first round and discusses the significance of the proposed exercises.

Reframing transition pathways

All first Living Lab workshops began with a presentation of local challenges, followed by a collective mind-mapping exercise where keywords trigger thematic exploration to produce a new frame. Case study teams pre-selected between 4 and 6 major drivers, such as “water”, “biodiversity” or “heatwaves”. Participants were asked to suggest new topics from the original ones, and to draw connections between topics, discussing and explaining reasons behind choices. The outcomes were an entwined, messy diagram representing a snapshot of the current state of the system from the participant's perspectives, and a draft problem statement based on the mapping activity.

Between workshops one and two, research teams worked on refined versions of maps and problem statements, validated by participants at the beginning of the second workshop. Maps and statements consistently showed that the core issues identified by participants did not fully match the researcher's initial hypothesis, revealing hidden blockers and blind spots underneath well-known issues. This result not only confirms the added value of the SIA for transition-framing processes, but also reveals how this type of action research positively impacts other methods and tasks carried out at the project's level.

A good illustration can be found in Case study 8's experience. Torbay&Devon County (UK), where this case study is located, is a coastal area highly vulnerable to flood. The ARSINOE research team studies the effects of flooding on the water supply network, the local environment, infrastructure and healthon Beyond the workshop's core exercise, team members involved in modeling activities wanted to take the opportunity to gather feedback on the model's design.

Figure 2. Workshop facilitator with participants.

Core ideas pre-selected by the local research team placed particular emphasis on flooding interactions, with “water”, “environment”, “health”, and “infrastructure” as the key drivers. During the exercise, however, the topic of “community” emerged as a central component of regional resilience, shifting the approach to modelling. Not only is “community” a new parameter to be incorporated in the models, but also, importantly, the very fact that an unforeseen driver may emerge triggers an evolution in the model’s structure to include new parameters on the fly over the course of the project.

Figure 3. Map of the system produced during the first Case Study 8 workshop.

Another interesting example was provided by Case Study 9 (Sardinia). This group works on the Water-Food-Energy nexus, with a specific focus on durum wheat production chain transformation to ensure optimization of water and land management, sustainability and production stability. The initial framing, “Food security in climate change conditions” focused on well-defined questions with known answers: Increasing yield, improving sustainable food production, adapting to climate change, enhancing short chains, raising awareness in consumers, and improving information on food safety. During the workshop, however, the group’s discussion shifted towards the need to grant good quality food access for everyone, a more complex socio-technical challenge that cannot be addressed through concrete, actions alone, but instead, requires a shift in the values underpinning food production and social relations in the region. Triggering a shift in stakeholders’ priorities, from initial concerns to more community-oriented values in which ensuring the right to food for everyone seems more important than economic growth alone.

Figure 4. Refined system map for CS9 elaborated from initial workshop inputs

Preliminary conclusions and next steps

Designing efficient transition pathways demands new forms of problem-framing that take full account of the complex reality of contemporary societies and environments. The System Innovation Approach provides a general framework to implement participatory research involving diverse stakeholders and perspectives. To achieve its full potential and trigger transformative actions, the methodology relies on local geographies, situated knowledges, and social dynamics.

Beyond local problem-solving, the implementation of the first round of SIA workshops in ARSINOE reveals that 1) reframing problems from a holistic perspective is essential to unveil major blockers and opportunities currently overshadowed by partial viewpoints; 2) community well-being and care are perceived as core drivers for collective action 3) finding new ways to tackle long-term social trends and transforming existing legal and financial frameworks, are crucial to leveraging positive transitions; 4) therefore, the main types of

innovations required to achieve resilience and successfully implement transition pathways are socio-technical, rather than technological, in nature.

The next steps involve shaping desirable future visions based on problems framed in the first workshop and co-designing the path from that vision to the present day, identifying milestones and innovation gaps. Outcomes from this process will help shape other ARSINOE tasks, such as modeling, governance analysis, innovation pathways, financial tools, and calls for innovations, all of which will have a direct impact on stakeholders and communities and may become examples of best practices for other regions, in Europe and beyond. In this sense, we expect to maximize the impact of this project, facilitate inclusive transitions, and produce better research.

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